

EIC User Group Newsletter

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NEWS

- Due to the Covid-19 lockdown, also the [second “Yellow Report” workshop](#) at Pavia Univ. (Pavia-Italy) was held on May 20-22 only in “**remote mode**”. Despite this, the workshop was successfully run through all its schedule, with the plenary sessions of the first day **reaching almost 190 simultaneous connections**, and having not less than 150/160 in the last day. The day 2 was mostly devoted to parallel sessions. Several of them were **joint sessions** among subgroups of the Physics Working Group (**PWG**), or among subgroups of the Detector Working Group (**DWG**), as well as among subgroups of both PWG and DWG. Other plenary sessions were devoted to a **thorough discussion on detector complementarity, accelerator/IR design, and workflow** among PWG, DWG and the Software WG. The final part of the program included **summary talks from each WG** and a brief remark on **take-away messages and goals** for the next third “Yellow Report” workshop. All material can be found at the [Indico agenda](#). **Recordings** of all sessions can be found [here](#).
- In day 1 of the second “Yellow Report” workshop, the call for an **Expression of Interest (EoI)** for potential cooperation to EIC Detectors was discussed, following up discussion at the last EICUG meeting on April 23. The call will be **issued on May 31** after folding in the feedback from these discussions. The **deadline** is set on **November 1, 2020**. A status report will be given at the fourth “Yellow Report” workshop, UCB - Berkeley (USA). For more details, see [here](#).

- In the [concluding remarks](#) of the second “Yellow Report” workshop some **take-away messages** were outlined:
 - * the EIC continues to have an **excellent and growing science case**
 - * science points to **uniquely versatile accelerator/IR/detector design**
 - * all stakeholders agree that a **second IR and detector is desirable**
 - * progress with many **more integrated parallel session topics**
 - * progress in central and forward detector integration topics
 - * **goals for third YR workshop:** present mature studies of detector requirements from physics processes; balance detector concepts versus impact on physics measurements; discuss possible systematics reduction among complementary detector choices.
- In the [“Yellow Report” menu of the EICUG web page](#), one can find the **calendar** of the next “Yellow Report” workshops:
 3. 17-19 September 2020, CUA - Washington D.C. (USA)
 4. 19-21 November 2020, UCB - Berkeley (USA)
- A new **Charter Committee** is in place to update the EICUG Charter for the next phase of the EICUG after the DOE CD0. The Committee is **formed** by
 - * John Arrington (Argonne Nat. Lab. - US)
 - * Will Brooks (USM Valparaiso, Chile)
 - * Olga Evdokimov (Univ. of Illinois, Chicago - US)
 - * Yuji Goto (RIKEN, Japan)
 - * Barbara Jacak (LBNL & Univ. California at Berkeley - US)
 - * Richard Milner (MIT - US) (Co-chair)
 - * Marco Radici (INFN Pavia, Italy)
 - * Franck Sabatié (Saclay, France) (Co-chair)
 - * Sevil Salur (Rutgers Univ. - US)
 - * Daria Sokhan (Univ. Glasgow, UK)

The Charter Committee is preparing a **survey** on the EICUG organizational structure, on effectiveness of communications and meetings, on responsibility of membership, on voting procedures, etc.. This survey will be distributed to the whole EICUG probably in early June.

NEWS from the ELECTION & NOMINATION COMMITTEE

- The Committee has started to work on the upcoming election for the office of **International Representative** on the EICUG Steering Committee.
- The new term will start on **July 1st, 2020**. Yuji Goto has agreed to continue in his present term until June 30th, 2020.
- The nomination and election **process started in April 2020** and a call for nominations was sent out.

NEWS from the CONFERENCE & TALKS COMMITTEE

- Because of the Covid-19 lockdown, the **schedule** of next workshops and summer schools of interest for the EICUG has been **drastically modified**: many events have been **postponed** (sometimes with tentative dates) or **cancelled** completely (see below).
- In any case, for consulting the list of **open EICUG talks** see <http://www.eicug.org/web/events/open> . For a list of **previous EICUG talks** see <http://www.eicug.org/web/events/previous> (often including also a link to the presentation). If you wish to recommend a candidate, including yourself, or if in general you wish to suggest new speakers (including yourself) to be considered for future invitations, please contact the Conference & Talks Committee at eicug-talks@eicug.org . Here, you can find also the general [talks guidelines](#) .

NEWS from the SOFTWARE WORKING GROUP

- The **Uproot and Awkward Array Tutorial** on analyzing Root files with pure Python libraries for Nuclear Physics analysis, was held on April 8 by Jim Pivarski (Princeton). The tutorial was recorded. Details can be found at <https://indico.bnl.gov/event/8242/>

- The **Advanced Fast Simulations Tutorial** was held on April 21 by Dmitry Romanov (JLAB) and Kolja Kauder (BNL). The tutorial was recorded. Details can be found at <https://indico.bnl.gov/event/8243/>
- Recordings of previous tutorials are available at the Youtube channel of the EICUG: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCXc9WfDKdLXoZMGrotkf7w>

NEWS from the INSTITUTIONAL BOARD

- The **EICUG** currently stands at **1075 members**, from **224 institutions** in 31 countries. Theory members are approximately 25%, experimentalists 60%, experts in accelerators 14%, support 1%.

This is a pie chart illustrating how the 224 EICUG Institutions are split into the 6 world regions.

- Since April 2020, **eight new Institutions** have joined the EICUG:
 - * Florida Agricultural and Mechanical University (US)
 - * Daresbury Laboratory (UK)
 - * University of Liverpool (UK)
 - * Rutherford Appleton Laboratory (UK)
 - * Shinshu University (Japan)
 - * Texas A&M University - Commerce (US)
 - * Centro de Investigación y de Estudios Avanzados del IPN (Mexico)
 - * Brunel University London (UK)

RECENT WORKSHOPS/MEETINGS of INTEREST

See also <http://www.eicug.org/web/events/previous> (includes also links to some presentations)

Those events labeled by were held with on-line only format.

[Correlations in Partonic and Hadronic Interactions \(CPHI-2020\)](#), CERN-Geneva (Switzerland), 3-7 February 2020

[2020 Santa Fe Jets and Heavy Flavor Workshop](#), Santa Fe (NM - US), 3-5 February 2020

[Winter Workshop on Nuclear Dynamics](#), Puerto Vallarta (Mexico), 1-7 March 2020

[1st EIC Physics and Detector Conceptual Development Workshop](#), Philadelphia (MD-US), 19-21 March 2020

[DIS 2020](#), Brooklyn (NY- USA), 23-27 March 2020 **Cancelled**

[Rencontres de Moriond, QCD and high-energy interactions](#), La Thuile (Italy), 28 March - 4 April 2020 **Cancelled**

[Jet observables at an Electron Ion Collider](#), Upton (NY - US), 15-17 April 2020 **Cancelled**

[QCD Evolution 2020](#), Los Angeles (CA - US), 27 April - 1 May 2020 **Cancelled**

[Streaming Readout VI](#), 13-15 May 2020

[2nd EIC Physics and Detector Conceptual Development Workshop](#), Pavia (Italy), 22-24 May 2020

UPCOMING WORKSHOPS/MEETINGS of INTEREST

See also <http://www.eicug.org/web/events/upcoming> and <http://cnr2.kent.edu/~manley/BRAGmeetings.html> (the latter is temporarily not updated due to the current “stay at home” order)

The events labeled by will be held only on-line.

[Origin of the Visible Universe: Unraveling the Proton Mass \(INT-20-77W\)](#), INT Seattle (WA - US), 4 - 8 May 2020 **Postponed**

[Transversity 2020](#), Pavia (Italy), 25-29 May 2020
Postponed to May 2021

[Joint GlueX-PANDA-EIC Workshop on Machine Learning for Particle Physics Experiments](#), Darmstadt (Germany), 25-29 May 2020 **Postponed**

[Hard Probes](#), Austin (TX - USA), 31 May - 5 June 2020

[Workshop on Pion and Kaon Structure Functions at the EIC](#), CFNS-Stony Brook (NY-US), 2-5 June 2020

[Tomography of light nuclei at an EIC](#), ECT*-Trento (Italy), 15-19 June 2020 **Postponed** to 25-29 October 2021

[LXX International Conference NUCLEUS-2020](#), Saint Petersburg (Russia), 26-30 June 2020 **Postponed** to 11-17 October 2020

[Light-Cone 2020](#), Jeju (Korea), 29 June - 4 July 2020
Postponed to 14-18 December 2020

[Beam polarization and polarimetry at EIC](#), CFNS-Stony Brook (NY-US), 26 June, 29 June, 1 July, 2020

[9th International Conference on New Frontiers in Physics \(ICNFP 2020\)](#), Kolymbari (Crete - Greece), 27 July - 7 August 2020

[40th International Conference on High Energy Physics \(ICHEP 2020\)](#), Prague (Czech Republic), 28 July - 6 August 2020

[EIC Users Group Meeting 2020](#), Miami (F - USA), 3-7 August 2020

[Photonuclear Gordon Conference](#), Holderness (NH - USA), 9-14 August 2020 **Cancelled**

[22nd International Conference on Particles and Nuclei \(PANIC2020\)](#),
Lisbon (Portugal), 31 August - 4 September 2020
Postponed to 30 August - 3 September 2021

[24th International Spin Symposium SPIN2020](#), Matsue (Japan), 20-25
September 2020 **Postponed** to 2021

[Baryon 2020](#), Sevilla (Spain), 22-25 September 2020

[New Physics Phenomena - Hadronic Contributions to New Physics
Searches](#), Crete (Greece), 24-30 September 2020

[The 17th International Workshop on Hadron Structure and Spectroscopy](#),
Trieste (Italy), 16-18 November 2020

[Lepton-Photon 2021](#), Manchester (UK), 9-14 August 2021

Quarks and Nucleon Physics QNP 2021, Bonn (Germany), 20-24
September 2021

UPCOMING SCHOOLS of INTEREST

[HUGS 2020](#), JLab-Newport News (VA-US), 1-19 June 2020 **Cancelled**

[National Nuclear Physics Summer School 2020](#), UNAM-Mexico City (Mexico), 22 June - 2 July 2020

[The Second CFNS Summer School on the Science of the Future Electron-Ion Collider](#), CFNS-Stony Brook (NY-US), 27 July - 5 August 2020

[Hadron Collider Physics Summer School](#), Fermilab-CERN, 10-21 August 2020

[MCnet-CTEQ Summer School 2020](#), Bad Herrenalb (Germany), 2-12 August 2020 **Cancelled**